

CONVALV: Development of a Mobile Pipeline Based on Artificial Intelligence for Non-Invasive Analysis of Heart Sounds using Deep Learning

Roberto Martín Gutiérrez

Summary

Cardiac auscultation is a widely used non-invasive tool in cardiovascular assessment, although its diagnostic reliability depends on the practitioner's experience and the conditions under which the auscultation is performed. Recent advances in artificial intelligence and mobile technologies allow for mitigating these limitations through automated, scalable, and accessible screening systems. This paper presents **CONVALV**, an application integrated into a functional web platform for the automatic analysis of heart sounds acquired via consumer devices. The system implements a mobile-to-AI pipeline. This architecture encompasses acoustic signal conditioning, hybrid extraction of physiologically interpretable features, and inference using deep learning models, providing rapid and reproducible screening results accessible through a digital interface. The proposed architecture is optimized for execution in computationally limited environments and geared towards future integration into telemedicine scenarios. Evaluation is performed using public reference datasets under rigorous subject-level validation protocols. Although CONVALV is presented as a research prototype and not a medical device, the results obtained demonstrate the technical feasibility of integrating automated analysis of non-invasive cardiac auscultation into digital platforms that support clinical decision-making.

Keywords: Cardiac auscultation; artificial intelligence; deep learning; telemedicine; biomedical signal analysis; mobile platforms.

1. Introduction

Cardiovascular diseases (CVDs) represent one of the greatest global health challenges, accounting for a significant proportion of mortality and disability in the adult population [1]. Despite advances in medical imaging techniques and invasive and non-invasive diagnostic methods, the early detection of cardiac abnormalities remains a challenge, especially in primary care, outpatient follow-up, and resource-limited settings. In this context, cardiac auscultation maintains a central role as a fundamental clinical tool due to its non-invasive nature, low cost, and ease of implementation in both hospital and outpatient settings [2].

However, the diagnostic utility of auscultation is closely linked to the experience of the healthcare professional and the quality of the acoustic acquisition. Previous studies have revealed high inter- and intra-observer variability in the identification and interpretation of murmurs, splitting, and other relevant acoustic phenomena, which limits its reliability as a systematic screening tool. Furthermore, factors such as ambient noise, sensor position, the patient's chest morphology, and the type of acquisition device can significantly degrade signal quality, hindering the extraction of clinically relevant information from recordings made outside of controlled environments.

The development of advanced digital signal processing techniques and, more recently, deep learning, has driven research into automated systems capable of objectively and reproducibly analyzing heart sounds. In particular, the use of spectro-temporal representations combined with convolutional neural networks has shown high potential for detecting acoustic patterns associated with valvular and structural pathologies. However, a considerable portion of the existing literature focuses on experimental setups using specialized digital stethoscopes or databases obtained under controlled acquisition conditions, which limits the transfer of these methods to real-world scenarios characterized by high heterogeneity and noise.

In parallel, the consolidation of mobile platforms and web applications in the field of digital health has opened new possibilities for the development of remote screening and monitoring solutions. The integration of data acquisition, processing, and visualization capabilities in app-web systems allows for the design of telemedicine-oriented workflows, in which the collection of physiological signals can be performed in a decentralized manner and their automated analysis can be carried out on scalable computing infrastructures. However, the design of these types of systems presents additional challenges, including the optimization of algorithms for limited computing environments, robustness against low-quality recordings, and the need to provide understandable and useful results for healthcare professionals.

In this context, it is presented **CONVALV**, an integrated app-web platform for the automatic analysis of heart sounds acquired through consumer devices, conceived as a mobile-to-AI pipeline and designed for digital health scenarios, the system combines signal conditioning techniques, hybrid extraction of physiologically interpretable features, and deep learning models engineered to operate efficiently in environments with limited computational resources. CONVALV is not intended as a replacement for clinical diagnosis, but rather as a tool to support screening and case prioritization, with a clear focus on future applications in telemedicine.

The aim of this work is to describe in detail the architecture and components of the CONVALV system, as well as to evaluate its technical feasibility using public reference datasets under rigorous validation protocols. Furthermore, it seeks to lay the groundwork for future research focused on clinical validation, the explainability of the artificial intelligence models employed, and the potential adaptation of the system to regulatory frameworks applicable to software-based medical devices.

2. System Architecture

The architecture of **CONVALV** is conceived as an end-to-end modular system that implements a mobile-to-AI pipeline for the automated analysis of heart sounds in digital healthcare environments, the system prioritizes a clear separation of responsibilities among its various components, facilitating its extensibility, maintenance, and independent optimization. The platform integrates an acquisition layer via mobile and web applications, an AI-based processing and inference core, and a visualization and reporting layer accessible through a digital interface.

The system **CONVALV** is structured as a modular pipeline composed of five main stages: (1) mobile audio ingestion and format normalization, (2) signal conditioning specific to heart sounds, (3) hybrid feature extraction, (4) inference using deep learning models, and (5) visualization and reporting of results. This organization allows for a systematic approach to addressing the inherent variability of acoustic recordings obtained in uncontrolled environments and facilitates the adaptation of the system to different deployment scenarios (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. General architecture of the CONVALV system and complete mobile-to-AI pipeline flow.

(1) Mobile audio ingestion and format normalization.

The first stage of the pipeline is responsible for receiving acoustic recordings from consumer devices, primarily mobile phones and low-cost external sensors. The system supports multiple compressed and uncompressed audio formats, so a normalization process is applied, including conversion to an uncompressed waveform format, standardization of the number of channels, and homogenization of the sampling rate. This stage ensures signal compatibility with subsequent modules and reduces the system's dependence on the acquisition hardware used.

(2) Specific signal conditioning for heart sounds.

Once normalized, the acoustic signal undergoes a conditioning process specifically designed for cardiac sound analysis. This module includes filtering techniques for suppressing low- and high-frequency noise, amplitude normalization, and attenuation of artifacts associated with the recording environment. The main objective of this stage is to improve the signal-to-noise ratio and highlight the relevant acoustic components associated with the cardiac cycle, providing a more stable signal suitable for subsequent information extraction.

(3) Hybrid feature extraction.

The third stage of the pipeline is based on a hybrid approach that combines learnable spectro-temporal representations with a set of engineered physiological features. On the one hand, dense time-frequency representations of the signal are generated, suitable for processing by convolutional neural networks. On the other hand, descriptors designed to capture global and local properties of the signal are calculated, such as temporal metrics, spectral statistics, and measures related to cardiac dynamics. This combination aims to balance model performance with the interpretability of the results.

(4) Inference through deep learning.

The resulting representations are fed into a dual-branch neural network model, in which each feature type is processed in parallel using specialized architectures. The intermediate outputs of both branches are merged into a common feature space, which feeds the final layers of the model responsible for generating a probabilistic estimate of the analyzed cardiac state. The model's design prioritizes computational efficiency, allowing it to run on low-power infrastructures and facilitating its integration into scalable web platforms.

(5) Visualization and reporting of results.

The final stage of the pipeline handles the visualization and reporting of inference results through the CONVALV web interface, which serves as the primary point of interaction between the system and the user on both mobile devices and desktop computers (www.convalv.com). This layer is implemented as a distributed, cross-platform web platform designed to decouple the presentation of results from the system's algorithmic core, thereby enhancing the scalability, maintainability, and security of the entire system (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. Public presentation webpage of the CONVALV platform. (Informative interface aimed at disseminating the system, accessing the analysis platform and contextualizing the use of artificial intelligence for the automated analysis of heart sounds).

From a technical standpoint, the user interface is developed as a modern web application based on frontend technologies geared towards dynamic content rendering and real-time interaction with the system's backend. This interface allows for the uploading of acoustic recordings, monitoring of the analysis status, and structured visualization of the results generated by the deep learning model, using synthetic visual indicators and interpretable summaries. The interface design prioritizes clarity, visual simplicity, and reduced cognitive load, avoiding overly technical representations and maintaining a clear separation from any automated clinical interpretation.

The business logic and execution of the analysis pipeline are managed through a separate backend, implemented as a web service that exposes application programming interfaces (APIs) for communication between the frontend and the processing modules. This backend handles analysis requests, validates input data, executes inference processes in a controlled manner, and returns results to the frontend. The architecture allows the deep learning model to be isolated from the presentation environment, facilitating its updating or replacement without affecting the interface layer.

The system is deployed on a virtual private server (VPS) infrastructure, configured to run both web services and inference modules in a controlled environment. This approach allows for complete control over computing resources, security management, and system scalability, while ensuring response times compatible with interactive use. Access to the platform is via a dedicated domain, which acts as a single point of entry to the system and facilitates its identification as an independent digital service.

In addition to displaying results, the web platform incorporates features designed to enhance the user experience and facilitate understanding of the analysis. These include an integrated help tab, which provides contextual information on how the system works and guides the user through the interaction process. A conversational module powered by artificial intelligence is also integrated, acting as an information assistant and offering general

explanations about the analysis flow and the meaning of the results, without providing clinical recommendations or automated diagnoses. The interface also includes a structured summary system that synthesizes the relevant information from the processed record, along with final explanation mechanisms designed to increase the system's transparency by highlighting the key elements that contributed to the results. These features enhance the platform's usability and interpretability, representing a further step towards the responsible adoption of artificial intelligence systems in digital health environments (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Interface of the conversational assistant integrated into the CONVALV platform.

From an architectural perspective, the separation between frontend, backend, and deployment environment allows the results visualization and reporting layer to evolve independently of the algorithmic core. This modularity lays the foundation for future expansions, such as the incorporation of user authentication mechanisms, secure storage of anonymized results, integration with external services, and adaptation to telemedicine workflows. Taken together, the implementation of this layer makes CONVALV a functional

digital platform, ready for evolution toward supervised clinical use scenarios and connected health services (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. CONVALV web interface for uploading acoustic recordings and managing automatic analysis.

3. Signal processing methodology and data set construction

Signal processing is a critical element in the system **CONVALV**, given that acoustic recordings acquired using consumer devices exhibit high variability in terms of noise, duration, amplitude dynamics, and overall quality, a processing pipeline specifically optimized for cardiac sounds has been designed [7] to ensure the robustness of subsequent analysis and the reproducibility of results. This pipeline integrates techniques established in the literature with practical criteria geared towards real-world mobile acquisition scenarios.

The audio signals are initially loaded and resampled at a frequency of 2000 Hz, corresponding to the native frequency of the PhysioNet/CinC dataset [3] and sufficient to capture the relevant spectral content of the heart sounds, including the components associated with the S1 and S2 tones, as well as any murmurs. To standardize the recording duration and facilitate comparative analysis, each signal is set to a fixed duration of 10 seconds. For longer signals, a central segment is selected, assuming it typically corresponds to a region of greater acoustic stability; for shorter signals, zero padding is applied until the target length is reached (see Figure 6).

Figure 5. Temporal representation of a conditioned cardiac signal and detection of cardiac cycle events.

Next, a conservative audio cleaning module is applied, designed to preserve relevant diagnostic information. This module includes a fourth-order Butterworth bandpass filter in the 20–500 Hz range, aimed at eliminating very low-frequency components associated with movement and breathing, as well as irrelevant high-frequency noise. Subsequently,

non-finite values are removed, and gentle amplitude normalization is performed, avoiding aggressive procedures that could distort the signal's temporal morphology.

A cardiac event detection procedure based on the Shannon envelope is implemented on the conditioned signal, following approaches widely used in cardiac sound segmentation [4]. After further filtering in the cardiac band, the energy envelope is calculated and temporal smoothing is applied using a moving window. The resulting peaks are interpreted as candidate cardiac events, allowing the estimation of physiological parameters such as heart rate and rhythm variability metrics, including the standard deviation of normal intervals (SDNN). Signals in which a minimum number of events are not detected are discarded to avoid introducing low-quality samples into the dataset.

Feature extraction is based on a hybrid approach that combines physiologically motivated spectral and temporal descriptors. In the spectral domain, the short-duration Fourier transform is calculated, and the average energy is extracted in frequency bands associated with the S1 and S2 components and heart murmurs, as well as energy ratios of diagnostic interest. Additionally, global metrics such as the spectral centroid and spectral entropy are included, used as indicators of the signal's complexity and frequency distribution. In the temporal domain, basic signal statistics, zero-crossing metrics, and systolic-diastolic ratio estimates are calculated from the intervals between detected events.

Additionally, for each recording, a time-frequency representation is generated in the form of a Mel spectrogram, calculated with parameters adapted to the sampling frequency used and limited to a maximum range of 500 Hz. These spectrograms are normalized and stored as numerical matrices, constituting the visual input for the deep learning model (see Figure 6). In this way, the final dataset integrates both explicit numerical features and dense representations suitable for processing by convolutional neural networks.

Figure 6. Time-frequency representation of a cardiac signal using Mel spectrogram and spectral density.

The complete processing pipeline is applied to the public datasets from the PhysioNet/CinC Challenge [3], incorporating available clinical information, such as age and gender, when present. Samples are labeled into normal and abnormal categories following the original annotations and stored along with their corresponding descriptors in structured formats (CSV and JSON). This procedure results in a curated and reproducible dataset, specifically designed for training and evaluating cardiac classification models within the CONVALV platform.

4. Feature Extraction

The system **CONVALV** employs a multimodal feature extraction strategy based on two complementary representations of the cardiac acoustic signal, aiming to capture both complex, high-dimensional patterns and physiologically interpretable descriptors. This approach seeks to balance model performance with the interpretability of the results, a particularly relevant aspect in clinical support and telemedicine applications.

First, dense time-frequency representations are generated in the form of Mel spectrograms, which provide a structured description of the signal's spectral distribution over time. These representations are particularly well-suited for processing by convolutional neural networks, as they allow the model to automatically learn local and global patterns associated with cardiac cycle dynamics, including temporal transitions and characteristic spectral variations [6].

Additionally, a small set of engineered features designed to capture relevant physiological properties of the signal is extracted. These variables include metrics related to heart rate variability, global spectral descriptors, energy ratios in clinically relevant frequency bands, and basic time-domain statistics. This feature set provides explicit, low-level information that is useful both for stabilizing model training and for facilitating the interpretation of the results.

Both representations are processed in parallel within the deep learning model and subsequently integrated into a common representation space, allowing the final decision to be based on a combination of automatically learned information and physiologically motivated descriptors. The detailed configuration of the model and the input representations used is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Configuration of the deep learning model and input representations used in CONVALV

Component	Description
Model type	Multimodal architecture for binary classification
Input representations	Time-frequency spectrograms and aggregated physiological variables
Spectral processing	Deep and efficient convolutional neural network
Variable processing	Multilayer perceptron for numerical features
Merger strategy	Integration of embeddings into a common space

Decision layers	Dense blocks with progressive regularization
Objective function	Robust loss function against class imbalance
Optimization strategy	Adaptive optimization with regularization
Overshoot control	Regularization and early termination
Model output	Probabilistic estimation for binary classification

This hybrid extraction approach allows CONVALV to leverage the generalizability of deep learning-based models without sacrificing explicit descriptors with physiological meaning, providing a flexible and extensible basis for future improvements aimed at explainability, clinical validation, and adaptation to different deployment scenarios [5].

5. Deep Learning Model

The proposed deep learning model, called **EfficientCardiacNet**, is specifically designed to address the multimodal nature of the heart sound classification problem in the context of the CONVALV platform [8]. The architecture is based on the premise that information relevant to the detection of pathological patterns is distributed across both high-dimensional spectro-temporal representations and low-level physiological descriptors, and that both types of information must be coherently integrated within the same decision framework.

For processing time-frequency representations, EfficientCardiacNet incorporates a convolutional branch dedicated to spectrogram analysis. This branch consists of a sequence of convolutional blocks designed to progressively extract local and global features from the acoustic signal, capturing temporal variations and spectral patterns associated with cardiac cycle dynamics. The use of spatial reduction and global aggregation operations results in a compact and robust embed, suitable for subsequent integration with other data sources.

In parallel, the model includes a second branch based on a multilayer perceptron for processing engineered features. This branch operates on a small set of numerical variables that summarize relevant physiological properties of the signal, providing a low-level representation that complements the information automatically learned by the convolutional network. The architecture of this branch is designed to stabilize the training and enhance the model's sensitivity to global patterns that may not be easily captured in the spectral domain.

The outputs from both branches are concatenated in a common representation space, where the embeddings learned from the spectrograms are combined with the explicit physiological descriptors. This early fusion allows subsequent layers of the model to learn nonlinear interactions between both sources of information, facilitating more informed decision-making. The final classification block consists of several dense layers with progressive regularization, whose function is to transform the joint representation into a probabilistic estimate associated with the sample's membership in one of the two considered classes (see Figure 7).

Figure 7. EfficientCardiacNet model architecture based on a dual-branch multimodal structure. (Parallel processing of spectrograms using a convolutional network and of physiological features using a multilayer perceptron, with fusion in a common representation space).

The model output is formulated as a continuous probability, which facilitates its interpretation as a relative risk indicator and allows the decision threshold to be adjusted according to the application context (see Figure 8). Consistent with the overall CONVALV approach, EfficientCardiacNet is not intended as a substitute for clinical judgment, but rather as an analytical component designed to support case screening and prioritization. The model design prioritizes computational efficiency and stability during training, laying the groundwork for its future integration into web platforms and mobile applications geared toward telemedicine scenarios.

Figure 8. Example of displaying results of the automatic analysis in the CONVALV web interface.

6. Experimental Evaluation and Results

The experimental evaluation of the proposed system was carried out with the aim of analyzing both the performance of the deep learning model and the practical feasibility of the complete pipeline in a realistic use case. For this purpose, the dataset from **PhysioNet/Computing in Cardiology Challenge 2016** was used, widely used as a reference in the literature for heart sound classification tasks, allowing for indirect comparison with previous work.

To avoid information leakage and overestimating model performance, a strict subject-level separation strategy was adopted, ensuring that recordings from the same individual did not appear simultaneously in the training and validation sets. This criterion is particularly relevant in biomedical signal analysis, where within-subject dependency can induce significant bias if not adequately controlled. Evaluation was performed using stratified cross-validation, preserving the class distribution within each partition.

The model's performance was quantified using standard metrics for binary classification problems in the clinical setting, including accuracy (*accuracy*F1-score, sensitivity, specificity, and area under the ROC curve (AUC) are also included. This set of metrics allows for a balanced characterization of the system's behavior, taking into account both its overall accuracy and its performance against potentially unbalanced classes, as well as its sensitivity to false negatives and false positives. The use of complementary metrics is essential in screening scenarios, where errors can have different clinical implications depending on their nature.

In addition to predictive performance, the computational efficiency of the entire system was evaluated. Latency measurements included all stages of the pipeline, from signal loading and conditioning to model inference and final output generation. Experiments were performed on general-purpose hardware representative of web and mobile application deployment environments, with execution times consistent with interactive use. In particular, the total processing time per sample remained on the order of seconds, supporting the system's viability for near real-time analysis scenarios.

The results show a robust and balanced system, with an overall accuracy of 96.0% and an F1-score of 0.974, indicating a favorable trade-off between precision and sensitivity even in the presence of class imbalance.

The confusion matrix analysis reveals a high capacity of the model to correctly identify normal and anomalous records. In the validation set, 2624 true positives and 776 true negatives were obtained, compared to 40 false positives and 101 false negatives. These results translate to a sensitivity of 96.3% and a specificity of 95.1%, values that are especially relevant in screening scenarios, where it is critical to minimize the omission of potentially pathological cases without generating an excess of unnecessary alarms.

The normalized confusion matrix confirms this behavior, showing classification rates above 95% in both classes (see Figure 9). In particular, the false negative rate remains low, reinforcing the system's suitability as a tool to support initial screening, where early detection takes precedence over exhaustive classification of specific pathologies.

Figure 9. Normalized confusion matrix of the binary classification model evaluated on the validation set.

Analysis of the confusion matrices obtained by applying more restrictive confidence thresholds reveals the direct impact of the required certainty level on the system's behavior. Increasing the confidence threshold (e.g., $\geq 70\%$ and $\geq 80\%$) leads to a progressive reduction in the number of predictions issued, accompanied by an improvement in the accuracy of the classifications. In particular, the number of false positives decreases consistently, while the proportion of true positives and true negatives among high-confidence predictions remains high. This behavior reflects a controlled trade-off between coverage and reliability, allowing the system to prioritize decisions with a higher degree of certainty. From a screening perspective, this strategy is especially relevant, as it allows the system to be adapted to scenarios where fewer predictions with higher reliability are preferred, leaving lower-confidence cases for further review or the acquisition of new recordings.

The analysis of the ROC curves (see Figure 10) and Precision-Recall curves (see Figure 11) demonstrates the model's high discriminatory power. An AUC-ROC of 0.989 was obtained,

indicating near-perfect separation between classes across a wide range of decision thresholds. Additionally, the Precision-Recall curve shows an area under the curve of 0.997, significantly higher than the baseline associated with the prevalence of the positive class, suggesting particularly robust performance in unbalanced data contexts.

Figure 10. ROC curve of the proposed deep learning model.

Figure 11. Precision-Recall curve of the heart sound classification model.

Finally, the decision threshold analysis shows that an optimal value around 0.45 maximizes the F1-score, allowing the system's behavior to be adjusted according to the context of use. This result highlights the model's flexibility in prioritizing sensitivity or accuracy based on the requirements of the clinical scenario, a particularly relevant feature for its future integration into screening and telemedicine workflows.

Taken together, these results confirm that the proposed system achieves high and consistent performance, supporting its technical viability as an automated analysis tool for heart sounds in digital environments, and establishing a solid foundation for future stages of clinical validation and controlled deployment.

7. Ethical considerations and limitations

The development of automated systems for cardiac screening raises important ethical considerations that must be explicitly addressed, especially when geared towards digital health contexts and potential telemedicine applications [9]. Among the main risks associated with these technologies are the potential to generate a false sense of security in users with erroneously negative results, as well as the induction of unwarranted anxiety in cases of false positives. These effects can be amplified when the tools are used outside of supervised clinical settings, underscoring the need for responsible design and clear communication of the system's capabilities and limitations.

In this work, **CONVALV** is explicitly positioned as a research prototype focused on the technical exploration of automated methods for analyzing heart sounds. The system is not intended for clinical diagnosis or autonomous medical decision-making and should be understood solely as an experimental support tool [10]. Consequently, no prospective clinical studies have been conducted, nor has regulatory approval been sought under the regulatory frameworks applicable to software-based medical devices [11].

Furthermore, the system has inherent limitations due to both the dataset used and the methodological approach adopted. The evaluation is based on retrospective data and annotations provided by third parties, which may not fully reflect the variability present in real-world acquisition scenarios. Additionally, the model focuses on a binary classification task, which restricts its ability to differentiate between multiple pathologies or degrees of severity. These limitations highlight the need for future research aimed at expanding the spectrum of classes, controlled clinical validation, and explainability analysis of the models before considering any use in real-world healthcare settings. These limitations, along with their implications and associated lines of work, are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2. Limitations of the CONVALV system and associated research objectives

Scope	Identified limitation	Implications	Future goal / line of work
Data	Use of a retrospective and public dataset	It may not reflect the acoustic, demographic, and clinical variability of real-world environments.	Prospective validation with data acquired in clinical and extraclinical settings
Data	Normal/anomalous binary annotations	Limitation in detailed clinical characterization	Extension to multiclass classification and stratification by pathology

Data	Uncontrolled heterogeneity of the acquisition device	Variability in recording quality and noise	Incorporation of automatic signal quality assessment modules
Data	Lack of complete clinical context	Lack of longitudinal information and comorbidities	Integration of additional clinical variables when available
Model	Dataset-dependent supervised approach	Possible bias towards dominant patterns in the data	Exploration of semi-supervised and self-supervised approaches
Model	Limited interpretability of the model	Difficulty in explaining decisions at a clinical level	Incorporation of explainability techniques and activation visualization
Assessment	Validation exclusively offline	The impact on real workflows is not evaluated	Pilot studies in real-world use scenarios
Scalability	Evaluation in general-purpose hardware	Performance not validated in hospital settings	Optimization and testing in clinical infrastructures
Clinical integration	No integration with hospital information systems	Difficulty in adoption in clinical practice	Development of interfaces compatible with HL7/FHIR standards
Interoperability	Lack of semantic normalization	Limited interoperability between systems	Alignment with standardized clinical data models
Regulation	Non-alignment with MDR/CE frames	Limited use for research	Regulatory analysis and design compliant with medical software requirements

Clinical use	Not validated as a decision support tool	Risk of misuse or overinterpretation	Definition of supervised clinical use cases
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Analysis of limitations and projection to real clinical settings

The limitations identified in the CONVALV system are consistent with the current state of research in automated heart sound analysis and reflect challenges widely described in the literature. While the use of public and retrospective datasets allows for reproducible and comparable evaluation, it imposes restrictions in terms of clinical representativeness and generalizability. Similarly, the lack of integration with hospital information systems and interoperability standards, such as HL7 or FHIR [12], limits the system's immediate applicability in real-world clinical settings.

However, these limitations explicitly define a roadmap for future research, focused on prospective clinical validation, improving the model's interpretability, and integrating the system into digital healthcare ecosystems. In particular, adapting the CONVALV pipeline to clinical interoperability standards and evaluating it in real hospital workflows are key steps in moving from a research prototype to a clinical support tool that meets current technical, ethical, and regulatory requirements.

8. Conclusions

This work demonstrates the technical feasibility of a mobile-to-AI pipeline for the automated analysis of non-invasive heart sounds, integrated into a digital platform geared towards connected healthcare scenarios. Through the combination of robust signal processing techniques, hybrid feature extraction, and multimodal deep learning models, the system **CONVALV** is capable of analyzing acoustic recordings obtained through consumer devices and generating reproducible estimates in times compatible with interactive use.

The experimental results obtained using publicly available reference datasets support the potential of the proposed approach as a tool to assist in screening and prioritizing cases, without intending to replace clinical judgment. The system's modular design, along with its web-based app implementation, facilitates its scalability and adaptation to different deployment contexts, including future applications in telemedicine.

Future work will focus first on incorporating automated recording quality assessment mechanisms capable of detecting degraded or invalid signals during acquisition and providing feedback to the user. This will improve the reliability of the analysis and reduce error propagation in later stages of the pipeline. Additionally, the current model will be expanded to include multiclass classification schemes that differentiate between various cardiac pathologies and severity levels, moving from a binary screening approach toward more informative clinical representations.

Furthermore, the system is designed to scale through the progressive collection of anonymized data, acquired under ethical and data protection protocols, which will enrich the training set and improve the model's generalizability to diverse populations. This strategy of controlled data volume growth is a key element for the system's evolution and its adaptation to real-world clinical contexts, while simultaneously maintaining patient privacy.

Figure 12. Conceptual diagram of the future clinical integration flow of the CONVALV system. (Interaction between user/patient, CONVALV application, system backend and its integration with hospitals and clinics through HL7/FHIR interoperability standards).

Another key area of work is the integration of a dedicated mobile application, designed as an interface for acquiring and accessing the system. This application will facilitate interaction with users and healthcare professionals and enable its use in remote care settings. It is envisioned as part of an app-web ecosystem, geared towards its future integration as a digital service in collaboration with hospitals and clinics, facilitating its incorporation into existing healthcare workflows. Additionally, the development of a low-cost, portable hardware device for the standardized acquisition of heart sounds is planned. The goal is to collect new, high-quality data that will expand and improve the model's training, increase its generalizability, and advance towards progressive clinical validation.

Finally, the project envisions progressively improving the user experience and the interpretability of the results, incorporating more intuitive visualizations, explanations of model behavior, and traceability mechanisms for the analyses performed. Taken together, these future lines of work are fundamental to advancing toward more robust, scalable, and clinically relevant automated cardiac analysis systems, aligned with the technical, ethical, and regulatory requirements of real-world healthcare settings.

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USE:

- The CONVALV platform is publicly available at <https://www.convalv.com>.
- E-mail: convalv@outlook.com
- Telephone: +34 688943303